

Some Low-valent Organometallic Complexes of Palladium(0), Platinum(0) and Rhodium(I)

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Some low-valent organometallic complexes of Pd⁰, Pt⁰ and Rh^I have been prepared and their tentative structure are assigned using various physicochemical data. All Pd⁰ and Pt⁰ compounds are tetrahedral but compounds of Rh^I have square planar configuration. Oxidation state of metals in these compounds are determined iodometrically. The ligand 3-(4 pyridyl) 4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thione interacts with its thione tautomeric form with Pd⁰ and Pt⁰, but both thione and thiol tautomeric form reacts with Rh^I depending on the experimental conditions of the reaction. Metal-ligand vibrations in the far-infrared spectra of complexes have been reasonably assigned.

Organometallic complexes of platinum group metals are versatile homogeneous catalyst¹. Many Pd⁰ and Pt⁰ complexes undergo reactions involving either coordinative dissociation or coordinative addition². The reactions and catalytic properties of rhodium complexes in solution have also been the subject of a review³. The present study describes preparation and characterisation of some novel organometallic complexes of catalytic interest following previous report⁴.

Results and Discussion

Rh(Pφ₃)₃Cl undergo substitution reactions in solution to yield compounds having formula [Rh(Pφ₃)₂Cl]L (L=Py, DMSO, MeCN, C₂H₄, CO) reported earlier by Osborn *et al*⁵. In the present case, the three-coordinated species Rh(Pφ₃)₂Cl⁶ formed after dissociation of Rh(Pφ₃)₃Cl in benzene, readily replaces chlorine by the interaction of thiol group of tautomeric PPytTH, resulting deprotonation and mid-buff coloured complex [Rh(Pφ₃)₂(PPytT)] is formed. However, when excess of PPytTH is used, two Pφ₃ groups are replaced by thione tautomeric form of PPytTH giving brown compound [Rh(Pφ₃)(PPytTH)]⁷ (PPytT) again. However, all Pφ₃ groups could not be replaced. When the substitution reaction of Rh(Pφ₃)₃Cl is carried out in benzene-ethanol mixture using carbonylating agent, abstraction of carbonyl group occurs in presence of thiol tautomeric form of PPytTH forming deep yellow colour compound [Rh(CO)(Pφ₃)₂(PPytT)] and golden yellow coloured compound [Rh(CO)(Pφ₃)(PPytTH)(PPytT)]. One molecule of Pφ₃ group in M(Pφ₃)₄ (M=Pt or Pd) is easily replaced by thione form of PPytTH. But all Pφ₃ group of Pt(Pφ₃)₄ could not be replaced by PPytTH either by increasing stirring or using excess of ligand.

Magnetic moment of all the complexes were found to be diamagnetic suggesting d¹⁰-configura-

tion of Pd⁰, Pt⁰ and d⁸-configuration of Rh^I. When the suspension of complexes were treated with iodine solution in carbon tetrachloride, the violet colour of iodine was discharged in all cases indicating the presence of Rh^I, Pt⁰ and Pd⁰ electronic state. However, determination of oxidation state of rhodium in the complexes was found by titration with ceric ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator⁷. All the complexes were titrated for a two-electron charge. The zero valent state of palladium and platinum was also verified by iodometric and acidimetric titrations. It was found that 1 g-mol of [Pt(Pφ₃)₂(PPytTH)₂] reacts with 2 g-equiv. of iodine and the liberated 2 g-mol of PPytTH consume 2 g-equiv. of NaOH, suggesting zero oxidation state of platinum in the complexes. Calculation for other Pd⁰ and Pt⁰ complexes were also obtained following the reported method⁸. Solutions of all complexes (10⁻³M) in DMF were non-conduction.

The ligand field bands in electronic spectra are observed by charge transfer band giving little use in deciding the stereochemistry of these complexes. The charge transfer bands are observed at 30 300–28 810, 30 000–29 423 and 42 000 cm⁻¹ in Pd⁰, Pt⁰ and Rh^I complexes respectively. The intensity of charge transfer bands of the Pd⁰ and Pt⁰ complexes are very high and appears high degree of d-p mixing.

Infrared spectra: Some selected ir bands of interest are given in Table 1. A comparison of the ir bands of Pφ₃⁹, PPytTH and the corresponding Pd⁰, Pt⁰ and Rh^I complexes indicate the following. The ν_{NH} band of PPytTH observed as medium band at 3 060 cm⁻¹. disappears in the spectra of [Rh(CO)(Pφ₃)₂(PPytT)] and [Rh(Pφ₃)₃(PPytT)]. It is therefore, concluded that PPytTH interacts with Rh^I ion using its thiol tautomeric form via deprotonation of thiol hydrogen resulting metal sulphur bond.

Bonding through sulphur is also supported by considerable red-shifts of thioamide bands III and IV observed at 1 090 and 785 cm^{-1} in the ligand, and have main contribution from $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$. On complexation the 1 090 cm^{-1} band is shifted to lower frequencies by about 30–50 cm^{-1} , and the 785 cm^{-1} band by about 15–165 cm^{-1} . However, the potential thioamide bands I and II of PPytTH split on coordination and the degeneracy of this band is disturbed probably due to increase in CN and decrease in CS bond order having bonding through sulphur¹⁰. Thus, strong metal-sulphur bond is assumed for all the complexes. The medium bands at 1 685, 1 620 \pm 10 and 1 580 \pm 5 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C}\cdots\text{O}}$ support the presence of coordinated $\text{P}\phi_3$ molecule¹¹. The non-ligand band at 1 820 cm^{-1} in $(\text{Rh}(\text{CO})-(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytT}))$ is due to $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group¹².

In far-infrared spectra, two $\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$ (420, 360 cm^{-1}) and one $\nu_{\text{Pd-P}}$ (425 cm^{-1}) in $[\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{PPytTH})_2]$, two $\nu_{\text{Pt-P}}$ (380, 350 cm^{-1}) and one $\nu_{\text{Pt-S}}$ (320 cm^{-1}) bands in $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$ suggest C_{3v} -point group in tetrahedral structure. But two $\nu_{\text{Pt-P}}$ (410, 390 cm^{-1}) and two $\nu_{\text{Pt-S}}$ (340, 325 cm^{-1}) bands in $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$ and probably due to lower symmetry in Td.Str. In square-planar $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})-(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$, one $\nu_{\text{Rh-P}}$ (350 cm^{-1}) band suggests two $\text{P}\phi_3$ molecules being *trans* to each other, and two $\nu_{\text{Rh-P}}$ (385, 340 cm^{-1}) and one $\nu_{\text{Rh-S}}$ (300 cm^{-1}) bands in $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{L}]$ suggest C_{2v} -point

group in square-planar structure. In $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2(\text{PytT})]$, two doublets at (325m, 315m cm^{-1}) and one medium band (340 cm^{-1}) suggest that two thione forms of PPytTH molecules are at *cis*-position in probable square-planar structure.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or C.P. grade. 3-(4-Pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thione (PPytTH)¹³, $\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4$ ¹⁴, $\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4$ ¹⁵ and $\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}$ ¹⁶ were prepared by the reported methods.

Tris{3-(4-pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thione}triphenylphosphinepalladium(0). $[\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{PPytTH})_3]$: Benzene solutions of the complex $\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4$ and PPytTH were mixed in a molar ratio 1:3. The mixture was stirred for 4 h at 45°, then cooled in a refrigerator and the resulting yellow crystals were washed with ice-cold benzene and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 , m.p. 224° (Found: C, 60.01; H, 4.25; N, 14.88; Pd, 9.23. Calcd. for: C, 60.53; H, 4.24; N, 14.86; Pd, 9.38%).

3-(4-Pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thionetris(triphenylphosphine)platinum(0). $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{PPytTH})_3]$: Benzene solutions of $\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4$ and PPytTH were mixed in a molar ratio of 1:1. The mixture was stirred at 65° for 2 h, then cooled to room temperature to yield light yellow crystals, m.p. 85°d (Found: C, 65.00; H, 4.45; N, 4.52; Pt, 15.55. Calcd. for: C, 65.04; H, 4.53; N, 4.53; Pt, 15.77%).

Bis{3-(4-pyridyl)-4-Phenyl 1,2,4-triazole-5-thione}bis(triphenylphosphine)platinum(0). $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$: The pale cream coloured complex was

TABLE 1—MAJOR INFRARED BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF LIGAND COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{NH}	Thioamide Band*				$\nu_{\text{M-P}}/\nu_{\text{M-S}}$
		I	II	III	IV	
PPytTH	3 060mb	1 480s	1 290s 1 240m	1 090m	785m	—
$[\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$	3 080mb	1 510w 1 500w 1 490m	1 320w 1 290w 1 242m	1 040w	760m	425w (420w, 360w)
$[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$	3 110mb	1 475m 1 500w 1 480s	1 320m 1 290m 1 210w	1 060m	770w	420w (410w, 360w)
$[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$	3 100mb	1 520w 1 490m 1 480m	1 320m 1 290m 1 280m 1 210w	1 060m	760m	410w, 390w (340w, 325w)
$[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2]$	3 110mb	1 500w 1 480s	1 290m 1 210w	1 060m	770w	420w (410w, 360w)
$[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{PPytT})]$	—	1 480s 1 450m	1 260w	1 050w	710w	385w, 340w (300w)
$[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})_2(\text{PPytT})]$	3 160w	1 500s 1 470s	1 320m	1 040w	720m	340w (325w, 315w)
$[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytT})]$	—	1 475m 1 440m	1 250w	1 040w	720w	350w (300w)
$[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PPytTH})(\text{PPytT})]$	3 080w	1 500m 1 480m	1 260w	1 050w	730w	340w (320w)

* $\delta_{\text{NH}} + \delta_{\text{CH}} + \nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (Band I); $\nu_{\text{C=N}} + \delta_{\text{NH}} + \delta_{\text{CH}} + \nu_{\text{C-S}}$ (Band II); $\nu_{\text{C-S}} + \nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (Band III); $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ (Band IV).

prepared as above using $Pt(P\phi_3)_4$ and PPytTH in 1 : 2 molar ratio, m.p. 125° (Found : C, 60.72 ; H, 4.24 ; N, 9.10 ; Pt, 15.91. Calcd for : C, 60.63 ; H, 4.23 ; N, 9.12 ; Pt, 15.89%).

Tris{3-(4-pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thine} triphenylphosphineplatinum(0). $[Pt(P\phi_3)(PPytTH)_3]$: The light yellow coloured complex was prepared as above using excess of PPytTH and increasing stirring to 6 h, m.p. 139° (Found : C, 56.01 ; H, 3.92 ; N, 17.87 ; Pt, 16.01. Calcd. : for : C, 56.11 ; H, 3.93 ; N, 13.78 ; Pt, 15.99%).

Tris(triphenylphosphine)-3-(4-pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thionatorhodium(I). $[Rh(P\phi_3)_3(PPytT)]$: The mid-buff coloured complex was obtained using $Rh(P\phi_3)_3Cl$ and PPytTH in 1 : 1 molar ratio in benzene as above, m.p. 120° (Found : C, 70.52 ; H, 4.80 ; N, 5.01 ; Rh, 9.12. Calcd. for : C, 70.40 ; H, 4.81 ; N, 4.90 ; Rh, 9.02%).

3-(4-Pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thionatebis(triphenylphosphine)carbonylrhodium(I). $[Rh(P\phi_3)_2(PPytT)(CO)]$: Benzene solution of $Rh(P\phi_3)_3Cl$ and solution of PPytTH in ethanol and monoethyl ether of ethylene glycol (1 : 1) were mixed in equimolar ratio. The mixture was stirred for 2 h. at 85°, then cooled and the resulting deep yellow coloured solid was washed with ice-cold monoethyl ether of ethylene glycol and dried under reduced pressure, m.p. 240° (Found : C, 65.68 ; H, 5.01 ; N, 6.26 ; Rh, 11.54. Calcd. for : C, 66.07 ; H, 5.05 ; N, 6.16 ; Rh, 11.34%).

3-(4-Pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thionobis{3-(4-pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole}triphenylphosphinerhodium(I). $[Rh(P\phi_3)(PPytTH)_2(PPytT)]$: The leaf brown complex was prepared similar to $[Rh(P\phi_3)_3(PPytT)]$ using excess of PPytTH and increasing stirring time to 6 h (Found : C, 61.01 ; H, 4.16 ; N, 15.00 ; Rh, 9.01. Calcd. for : C, 60.74 ; H, 4.17 ; N, 14.92 ; Rh, 9.14%).

3-(4-Pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thionato-carbonyltriphenylphosphine-3-(4-pyridyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thionerhodium(I). $[Rh(CO)(P\phi_3)(PPytTH)(PPytT)]$: The golden yellow coloured complex was prepared following preparation of $[Rh(CO)(P\phi_3)_3(PPytT)]$ using excess of PPytTH and increasing stirring time to 6 h (Found : C, 60.11 ; H, 4.01 ; N, 12.53 ; Rh, 11.23. Calcd. for : C, 59.93 ; H, 3.99 ; N, 12.43 ; Rh, 11.43%).

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Backmann DU-6 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance ($10^{-3} M$) of complexes were measured in DMF using Wiss-Werkstätten Weihem Obb type LBR conductivity meter. Magnetic measurements were made on a Gouy balance using $Hg[CO(SCN)_4]$ as calibrant.

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